

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B110
Date: 13 Jul 2005
Take Off: 12:04:08
Landing: 15:41:55
Flight Time: 3h37m47s

Campaign: ICEPIC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Wales and SW England

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottoway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jonathan Smith	Leeds University
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	CVI/CCN	Paul James	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	AMS	Paul Williams	Manchester University
9	AMS Training	Gerard Capes	Manchester University
10	Mission Scientist 2	Phil Brown	Met Office
11	ADA / CPI	Mike Flynn	Manchester University
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B110 Track 13-JUL-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b110
 Date: 13/07/05
 Project: ICEPIC
 Location: SW & Wales

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
100918		Start posn	0.00 kft	127	52'04.36 N, 0'37.48W
114411		INU	0.02 kft	127	Set to Navigate
120408		T/O	0.57 kft	290	Cranfield
120922		ASPs	5.0 kft	265	Open
121055		AMS	5.0 kft	268	Started logging
121136		AMS	5.0 kft	266	on Rosemounts
121605		Nevz	5.0 kft	177	Zero cal
121754		Videos	5.0 kft	178	Start FFC & RFC
124512		AMS	12.0 kft	288	To CVI Inlet
124607		Cals	12.0 kft	293	JW & Nevz calcs
124600	124945	Run 1.1	12.0 kft	296	JW & Nevz calcs
125301	125554	Run 1.2	13.0 - 13.1 kft	152	JW & Nevz calcs
130133	130238	Run 1.3	14.3 - 14.4 kft	352	JW & Nevz calcs
130639	130745	Run 1.4	15.0 - 15.1 kft	176	JW & Nevz calcs
131213	131438	Run 1.5	15.0 - 15.1 kft	337	JW & Nevz calcs
131811	132005	Run 1.6	15.2 kft	102	JW & Nevz calcs
132309	132438	Run 1.7	15.3 kft	305	JW & Nevz calcs
134227	134334	Run 2.1	12.0 - 12.1 kft	240	JW & Nevz calcs
134714	134828	Run 2.2	11.3 kft	050	JW & Nevz calcs
140532	140738	Run 3.1	11.0 - 11.1 kft	019	JW & Nevz calcs
141031	141404	Run 3.2	11.1 kft	355	
141515	141913	Run 4.1	11.5 kft	070	JW & Nevz calcs
141946	142105	Run 4.2	11.5 kft	354	JW & Nevz Cals
142114	142141	Run 4.2	11.5 kft	001	
142621	143034	Run 4.3	13.0 kft	189	JW & Nevz calcs
143432	143840	Run 4.4	14.5 kft	073	JW & Nevz calcs
144226	144713	Run 4.5	16.1 kft	183	JW & Nevz calcs
145019		Turb P	14.2 kft	103	AOSS iced up Descend to clear it
150241	150317	Run 4.6	15.2 kft	025	JW & Nevz calcs
151122		Videos	15.0 kft	138	Change tapes
151220	151825	Run 4.7	15.1 kft	087	JW & Nevz calcs
151836	152754	Profile 1	15.0 - 5.0 kft	102	1000fpm
151925		AMS	14.2 kft	100	To Rosemount inlet
152754	153522	Run 5.1	5.0 - 5.1 kft	065	1000fpm
152907		CCN	5.0 kft	083	Sample starts
153714		ASPs	3.4 kft	096	Closed
153700		AMS	2.6 kft	094	Stop logging
154155		Land	0.08 kft	259	Cranfield
154613		Stop posn	0.07 kft	309	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B110 Track 13-JUL-05

5°W 4°W 3°W 2°W 1°W 0°

PROJECT BRIEF: ICEPIC – development of ice and precipitation in cumulus clouds.

Scientific Aims: The goal of ICEPIC is to understand and quantify the formation and growth of ice particles in cumulus clouds. We wish to examine:

- ❖ the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- ❖ the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- ❖ other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- ❖ the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- ❖ the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- ❖ the production of precipitation

As a first priority, in-situ aerosol and microphysical measurements from the aircraft will be gathered in close coordination with the CAMRa radar at Chilbolton, Hants. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C. The radar may identify columns of supercooled raindrops within the growing cumulus clouds that can be investigated more intensively by the aircraft.

Weather conditions: Developing showers that are forecast to have tops up to about -15°C within range of the Chilbolton radar. **A section of air free of ice crystals from higher or older clouds.** It may be preferable to fly to an alternative region away from the radar if conditions are more suitable.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. Information on current location of lightning (sferics) can be provided by FAAM using the NAMIS system. Several aircraft will be operating in the boundary layer at the same time as part of CSIP: UFAM Cessna - entire project; German DO-128 - 20 June to 17 July; NERC DO-228 - August. (The BAS Twin Otter may also participate in CSIP.)

Key instruments and their operation

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS (including cruciform), INU, turbulence probe
When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs to monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (loss of variability in signal). **ICEX to be used on radome, water traps empty.**
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC.
When straight & level in clear air, zero / calibrate and note in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC profile ascents or descents should avoid cloud if possible

Cloud Microphysics & Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP (or CIP-100), PCASP, SID-1.
Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, pristine ice crystal habits, large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery above freezing level.
- CPI as above
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator (2min reqd.) whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. **Requires altitude to be held for the 10 min of sample & process.**
- AMS minimum 2 min (~12km) reqd for size-resolved composition distribution (out of cloud or Option **B** runs)
- CVI below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode
above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode to sample cloud particle residues into the AMS

Key instruments currently unavailable

- *Ice Nucleus counter*
(INC) will normally be operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to different conditions.
- FWVS {to preserve lamp life, switch off when dew point above -15°C}
- ADA & SID-2 as for 2D probes

Quicklook to include: TATD & N, DP, LAT, LON, LWC, NEVLW & TW, U, V, W, PHGT, HDG, TAS, TBPC & PD

SORTIE BRIEF: ICEPIC ICE and Precipitation Initiation in Cumulus clouds

Flight Number: B110

Date: 13th July 2005

Mission Scientist: Jonathan Smith

Sortie Aims: To measure development of microphysics and dynamics in cumulus cloud systems.

Location: Amongst developing cumulus clouds within 1-5 hours transit of Cranfield. Alpha & Bravo areas.

Preference to be west of Chilbolton radar facility (to be within radar range). More likely over higher ground.

Sortie Summary:

1. Characterise inflow atmosphere around and below developing cumulus – *where not done by CSIP*
2. Penetrate cumulus clouds, preferably near the top of growing turrets, through the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be *with wings level*. Three principal options are for:
 - A well-defined isolated clouds
 - B many clouds (RICO scenario)
 - C organised convection on a convergence line or a gust front.

Meteorological information will be given from the CSIP Operations Centre at Chilbolton before flight and in-flight (using VHF radio, new frequency is 130.575 MHz, call-sign remains “Radsearch”).

Sortie Detail

1. Out-of-Cloud: only where not done by CSIP

- 1.1. Take off and climb for transit to the operating area. Locate suitable growing cumulus. 40+ min
- 1.2. *Optional profile descent in clear air, 1000 ft/min, FL200 to 500 ft agl. If necessary step profile to stay in area. (Not required at Chilbolton) Set altitudes and directions for later[†].* 25 min
- 1.3. Run at 500 ft agl, minimum **time 10 min** along suitable azimuth (across line or front for Option C) to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require initial delay to settle instruments. 10 min
- 1.4. Ascend to 500 ft below cloud base and carry out **10 min** run on suitable azimuth to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require delay after ascent to settle instruments. 15 min

2. Cloud Work Options

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with clouds, near their top

- A.1. Proceed to about 0° C altitude[†], or below max cloud top if lower 5 min
- A.2. Adjust altitude to 500 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude. It is important to penetrate the growing turret, updraught, region. Once clear of cloud, continue run for 10 s then procedure turn to come back to same region of cloud as quickly as possible. 5 min
- A.3. As time permits, repeat A.2, ascending with the top (if appropriate) until T = -20° C[†].
{ Vertical separation of repeats set to match growth of cloud} 45 min

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample many clouds

- B.1. Proceed to 0° C altitude[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min
- B.2. Commence 10 min run in along shear direction[†]. Adjust track to randomly sample growing turret / updraught regions of cloud but without passing through RED radar echoes (reflectivities of 37 dBZ or greater). End run clear of cloud. 10 min
- B.3. As time permits, repeat an ascent by -3° C[†] (approximately 1500 ft) followed by a run as in B.2 until the lowest of -15° C[†] or max cloud top is reached. (-3, -6, -9, -12, -15° C[†]) 75 min

Option C: Clouds with linear organization (eg. along a convergence line or gust front).

- C.1. Proceed to 0° C[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min
- C.2. Fly leg perpendicular to line, length as required. Adjust track to penetrate cloud tops or cell centres. End run clear of cloud. 2 min
- C.3. As time permits, repeat a 180° turn and ascent followed by C.2. Ascent either; as A to 500 ft below cloud tops until -20° C[†] reached, or as B at fixed temperature levels. 30+ min

3. Repeat If time permits, for new developing cumulus carry out Option A, B or C.

Transit return at any suitable altitude. 40+ min

Mission Scientist's Log

Jonathan Smith

Flight No **B.110**.....

Date **13th July '05**.....

Page **1** of **5**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1202	t/a	3500			hazy, 3/8 Cu
1206	distd	5000			above cloud base of Cu now 6/8 Ci, above tops of Cu also Cu maybe 300 ft deep, T from cockpit +19°C
1229					thru top of small cu T+12°C ↑ Horace
1215					v. hazy,
1224		5000			tops of Cu only 1-2000ft above us now
1227		5300			near most tops, some big blown to east
		8000			tops of overlying cloud, 1/8 Cu 2/8 Ci
		10000			T +4°C
				Alamb. " →	bird SW-NE tops 3-4k over Chulbatho "
					height looks good
					1h s thru panel, K's 2nd 3 rd panel bumped long 1 mi 10 4 th panel 65
					2D no ice (SID2 washes)
					CPI, just water, poor data
1255					poor back thru rain wear top several parts

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B. 110**

Date

 Page 2 of 5

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					2DC not a great
1302		14300			into cloud engine, 22 seconds across
	PHK	near tv	less than		Lv - drop collection efficiency
1306		15000			drop to get near top time to turn just miss top - did not grow much that time broad base
1309		15000		509°N 3.7°W	T _{air} 5°C Bar -16 (out of cloud and turn)
					3/8 Ci appears to be more directly above
1312					not much greater, but 1h s across 1m to get next 3 s over "next" turns
					will do both turns
					2D small stuff only 100 μm are biggest Now same sized
					try 500 ft too much
		15200			
151911	1-6				T-5 will skim 1 st + better into second / 5 s over 1 st /
					is it stuck on the hump in the profile
					that was 4 s

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.10**.....

Date

 Page **3** of **5**..

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					on a cloud that is stuck
					→ early connection actually Sol Norway
					N to Bonstaple
1337		12000			now T+0.65°C outside
					warmer than before (13 min since last)
					cloud pass
					Approaching - green yellow on radar, maybe 3 cells
					now some red on the radar
	R2.1				cloud is quite low → missed it
					down in a hazy layer now 11500 ft
	R2.2	112			took 3 seconds
					Leave the area its a bit to stable here! T+2.1
135218	trsd			19° 50.7'N 47°W	
					Click bottom → tops stuck at 15,000 ft - lid
	trsd	11000			T+1.3°C ← drop 1° over B. cloud
					cannot work a cloud in/near controlled airspace but
					will run through it since we are here
					not much echo, patch green
14:06					look like old cloud above from
					yesterday's storms?
					look like ~ 800 ft below top green yellow about run
					just into cloud id fun at edge
					How to go before return
		11000			2°
14:12:14	trsd				airway - pass don't drift overhang

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.110**

Date

 Page **4** of **5**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		11500	↗		some stratus coming off
	a new cloud				out of cloud at 2000 ft
					already rain
14:19:26	start again				go up to
					last 2 cells - no real wings
		FL130			T - 2.8°C
14:27:14	to kmel				good 600 ft below nuptea
14:30:08	lower down on				second cloud out + in
	then into				some stratus stuff
		FL130			T - 3.8°C
	700 Ci above				5-6 ms ⁻¹
	Phh #145				this is second patch
14:35:39	of these clouds				rain
	found video				iced up
14:36:34	onto next kmel				out then back in again
14:37:44	thru a top -				just edge of danger area
	do miss the				going thru to pod.
	rain on				blms on 23 s
14:46					6/8 Ci above looks stable
					clear
14:46:59		16000			10 s - blow
14:47	→	17000			v. little ice on probes
					88c has just cleared
14:55	looks ok now				80 return to FL170

Chilb. Ops
01264 862931

2nd Aircraft Scientist's Log

P
BROWN

Flight No **B.110**
FAAM © 2004

Date 13/7/05

Page 1 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1204					T/O Cranfield
		5000			Cloudbase ?
1214			180		Few Cs around initially but after turn S to Chilba going into clear area.
1216		5000			Seem to have region of Cs/Sc with some layers above ?
1219		"	180		Sign of Cs tops going to ~8-9000ft on the left
1229		8000			Cloud tops here.
1239		12000			-0.7°C Poss targets ahead in view on video.
124230		"			Some parts of cloud cluster may be just above freez-level.
1246		12000			Going into cloud, appears unglaciated - This is R1.1.
124945		"			End R1.1 Larger particles were water.
125301		13000			-2°C End Run - mostly rain in that cloud
					Cloud just into yellow.
		14300			
130133		14300			-3.4 Start 1.3 mostly water, Ntw is lower than New
		15000			-5.0 Start 1.4
					Skimmed over cloud tops.
		15000			Start 1.5

131438

End 1.5 2 clouds with a sharp turn.

2nd Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.110**

 Date **13/7/05**

 Page **2** of **3**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		15200		-5.5	R1.6 1 cell top,
				LWC	peaking around 1.2 each time
132309		15200		-5.5	R1.7 just through top.
1329					
1337		12000		0.8	Moved SW to get small growing cell.
/				0.8	Sea breeze over N Cornwall coast.
/					
1342		12000		1.5°C	Start 2-1 went just over top.
133714		11200		2.4°C	Start 2-2
1404		11000		+1.0	Going across Bro Cham thro unworkable cloud to new search area.
140532		11000			Start 3.1 looks unglaciated
/					Tops ~ 2000 above?
/					End 3.1 no cloud.
14031		11		-0.5	Start 3.2 NTW & NW close agreement on this leg when in cloud.
/					End 3.2
141517		11500		-0.3	Start 4.1 Just below layer of AC.
		11500			Start 4.2
142621		13000		-2.8	Start 4.3 Start 4.3
/					tops ~ 3000 higher?
/					End 4.3 2 or 3 cells
/				was	unglaciated.
		14500		-5.3	Start 4.4 Td -33
					1st top ~ 1000ft up.

133637

FF Video rec'd. Fms' updrafts.

2nd Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B. 11φ**
FAAM © 2004

Date 13/7/05

Page 3 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		16000		-8	
144715				-9	End R4.5
		17000			
1448					Turb probe iced in last cell. descend to FL100.
145530					Turb probe cleared, climb to 170 initially.
		16000		-7.5	Ta -16/17
		15000			Start 4.6 descended sharply just before dark.
/					Just probe for run across airway to see as many clouds as poss.
/		15000		-6.0	Start 4.7 1 cloud ahead.
/					Stratus layer ~ 1500 below
1517					1 pass complete.
151836		15000			Start Prof 1. to 5000
1525					Chillbolton abeam on R
/					took a few photos. Clouds don't look v. diff from those over Wales.
152754		5000			End P1 Start R5
/					Think this is just above base.
/					CEN sampling was prob ~ 200ft below base mostly.
/					End R5
/					Descent profile clearly shows stable layer at ~ 600 hPa. e just below
1542					land. 1500ft

3h 40m

clear why legs were stopping close to that level.
4000 kg fuel remains.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B110

Date: 09/08/05

Operator: MAP

Page 1 of 3

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID2	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:46:29											Start Run 1.1 @ FL120
12:48:00	1200	0.4	652		5	800	1	300	1000	1	
12:49:45											End of Run 1.1
12:53:01											Start Run 1.2 @ FL130
12:54:00	10	0.08	772								
12:55:54											End of Run 1.2
13:0133											Start Run 1.3 @ FL143
13:02:00	1110	0.39	1146		50	400	1	1800	600	1	
13:02:42											End of Run 1.3
13:06:39											Start Run 1.4 @ FL150
13:07:00	7	0.09									
13:07:45											End of Run 1.4
13:12:14											Start Run 1.5 @ FL150
13:13:00	1000	0.4	1291		10			200			
13:14:39											End of Run 1.5
13:18:11											Start Run 1.6 @ FL152
13:19:00	7	0.08	1313								
13:20:05											End of Run 1.6
13:23:09											Start Run 1.7 @ FL152
13:24:00	5	0.08	1378								
13:24:38											End of Run 1.7
13:42:28											Start Run 2.1 @ FL120
13:43:00	16	0.08	1402								
13:43:35											End of Run 2.1
13:47:14											Start Run 2.2 @ FL112
13:48:00	10	0.07	1411								
13:48:31											End of Run 2.2
14:05:33											Start Run 3.1 @ FL110
14:06:00	60	0.08									
14:07:38											End of Run 3.1
14:10:31											Start Run 3.2 @ FL110
14:11:00	370	0.48	1579		10	800	1	400	1800	1	
14:13:00	60	0.09	1582								
14:14:05											End of Run 3.2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B110

Date: 09/08/05

Operator: MAP

Page 2 of 3

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:15:15											Start Run 4.1 @ FL115
14:16:00	440	0.41	1716		10	800	1				
14:18:00	270	0.31	1180		13	800	1/11	900	800	1/11	
14:19:17											End of Run 4.1
14:19:51											Start Run 4.2 @ FL115
14:20:00	80	0.3	1936		13	600	1				
14:21:41											End of Run 4.2
14:26:21											Start Run 4.3 @ FL130
14:27:00	25	0.08									
14:29:00	18	0.08	2535								
14:30:35											End of Run 4.3
14:34:33											Start Run 4.4 @ FL145
14:35:00	22	0.09									
14:37:00	50	0.07	3365								
14:33:44											End of Run 4.4
14:42:29											Start Run 4.5 @ FL160
14:43:00	30	0.08	3406								
14:45:00	1000	0.40	3542		300	400	1	1000	1800	1	
14:47:00	11	0.08									
14:47:14											End of Run 4.5
15:02:42											Start Run 4.6 @ FL150
15:03:00	1000	0.53	3662		150	25	12				
15:03:17											End of Run 4.6
15:12:20											Start Run 4.7 @ FL150
15:13:00	10	0.08									
15:15:00	11	0.07									
15:17:00	18	0.07	3715								
15:18:24											End of Run 4.7
15:18:40	30	0.08									Start Profile 1 from FL150
15:19:31	35	0.08									FL140
15:20:29	60	0.08									FL130
15:21:28	25	0.08									FL120
15:22:21	90	0.08									FL110

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B110**

Date: 13/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	N	
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2		Y
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI		Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B110

Date: 13/07/05

Instruments

1. Video – inboard recorder screen in standby
2. Outboard video chewed tape pre-flight. Tried running a cleaning tape on it. It got chewed too!
Cleaned the spools using cotton buds & IPA.
3. FFC picture shows smudge in lower left corner. Debris or dirt on window?
4. CPI – Poor quality data, background unstable. May have got water in the probe
5. Flt Manager's pc display locked up @ 1303, rebooted pc then okay
6. SID 2 – pc kept crashing

AMS, CCN, CVI - okay

Aircraft

1. Rudder & Trim System problem – rectified pre-flight
2. Intercom – Captain's tx very quiet compared to Co's and radios.
3. Flight duration – landed with 4 tonnes fuel after 3h37 flight (fire cover avail for another hour)

Satcom H – ICEPIC made 4 calls

B110

Tephigrams - Tephigram Plot

Printed on 13 Jul 2005 at 18:25

130600 VT 131200 LARKHILL - 03743

131400 LARKHILL - 03743

RAINFALL RADAR IMAGES 14:30 to 17:30

Copyright NERC Satellite Receiving Station, University of Dundee
Channel 1,4,3 Received from Satellite Terra on Wed Jul 13 11:44:47 2005

